

VALENCE AND SYNTACTIC RELATIONSHIP

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Abstract. The concept of valence was not considered important to make our speech fluent and graceful. Not being able to use words correctly creates significant rudeness in our speech.

Keywords. Valence, semantic and syntactic valence, phraseology, dictionary meaning.

The valence theory entered linguistics at the end of the 40s of the last century [1, B.132]. In the valence theory, the property of a word attaching another word to itself is summarized [2, B.21].

The socio-practical, scientific value of language as a means of communication comes from the content plan of its units, from the expression of a concept. As a result of the substantial approach to the word, valence is evaluated as the internal possibility of the word, as a specific semantic property of the word. From speech units expressing complex concepts to speech units expressing thoughts, the occurrence is directly related to word valence. At the same time, the combination of words in speech is not an absolute phenomenon, but a relative one. Because the words are combined not with any words specified by the grammatical model, but with some of them [3, B.35]. So, the possibility of combining words is limited, and this is measured by the possibility of meaning of each word. More precisely, the connecting word semes have the ability to connect these semes in the structure of semes, there are semantic components (classes) common to both semes, and the semes of the semantic syntagm are interconnected through these semes, enter into a logical relationship [4, B. 94]. It seems that words combine semantically with some words to form a syntactic construction,

but with other words they form a commonality only by having the character of a linguistic fact, a nominative unit, that is, they do not enter into a logical relationship with each other. . Even when entering into such a relationship, it is only artificial, formal, and is not confirmed by various objective facts. Compare: a fat refrigerator, a quad bike, and reading a person.

The concept of a word is a common concept for all language levels, and its appearance as a lexical unit is known as a lexeme. The fact that there is no uniform (or general) view on the issue of words in linguistics means that it is a complex unit and that there are still many aspects that need to be studied. Difficulties in defining the word concept have led some linguists to abandon this concept. It is true that Ferdinand de Saussure, the founder of the sociological school of linguistics, hesitated to determine the place of the word in the language system. On the one hand, he evaluated the word as a concrete unit and showed it as the central element of the language system, on the other hand, after some comments about the word, he came to the conclusion that "the concrete unit of the language should not be looked for in the word" [5, B.35].

As the phenomenon of valence is based on the meaning of the word, if the concept of the word as a concrete unit loses its importance, the question arises as to how much this phenomenon can preserve its essence. But it should not be forgotten that the essence of valence is reflected in the process of connecting words. Therefore, valence is not an external phenomenon, but an internal phenomenon. Thinking about valence out of context is a mistake. Although the meanings contained in the semantic structure of a word create the possibility of its association with other words, this possibility lives in an unrealized form, and only in the structure of connected speech can the real meaning of the word and its relation to association be revealed. clearly reflected.

Initially, the theory of valence was divided into two directions - form and semantic direction, which solve the nature of valence in different ways. In the following periods, attention is paid to the mutual convergence between these two directions, the existence of the relationship between the valences of the word form and the lexical meaning of the word.

There are mainly two types of present tense: syntactic and semantic. Syntactic valency is the ability of a certain independent word to combine with another independent word and is also related to semantics. Semantic valency indicates various syntagmatic relations between lexemes. For example, the lexeme "sayramoq" in the Uzbek language means the sound of birds, that is, speaking. Therefore, he can only communicate with the word birds.

Semantic valency is the selection of semantically appropriate conjunctions of a connecting lexeme. For example, a vowel lexeme cannot attract a bird lexeme, and a bird lexeme cannot fall into any space in a vowel lexeme. Because there is no spiritual compatibility between them. In order for lexemes to be meaningfully compatible with each other, their meaning structures must contain similar meaning fragments - semes. Due to the fact that the ruler is in the attractor position, its valence is called the ruler valence, and the valence of the lexeme connected to it is called the subordinate valence.

Just as different terms can be combined only when they are compatible with each other, the linguistic unit should also be compatible in terms of meaning and grammar. In other words, a connecting lexeme requires that the lexeme to be connected should be compatible not only in terms of meaning, but also in the same grammatical form. Accordingly, valency is divided into lexical and syntactic layers.

Syntactic valency. Syntactic valence is the second side of lexeme valence, which requires that a lexeme in the dominant position needs to receive subordinate lexemes in a certain syntactic form - agreement, auxiliary, adjective, adjective. This governor is determined by the syntactic position and grammatical form of the lexeme.

Syntactic valence is closely connected with semantic valence, if one changes, the other changes, and if one does not exist, the other does not.

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